

Research Article

“The End of Education is Character”: Sathya Sai Baba.

Dr. G. Nageswar Rao

Dept. of Education, Meena Ketan degree College, Gurandi, Gajapati (Dist.) Odisha.

Corresponding Author: G. Nageswar Rao, Mail: dr.gnageswar@gmail.com

Abstract

In this world of declining morals and human values, where science and technology have advanced to the point where man is capable of destroying not only himself, but the entire world. What man truly needs today is not this external knowledge. He needs refinement of the heart. This can be got only by internal culture. It is not enough today to make a man a mere human being. He has to be transformed into an ideal human being. Education makes a man compassionate. That is the fulfilment of the purpose of education. Education should not be equated with book knowledge or the acquisition of skills for leading one's life in the world. The modern student is unable to determine what is the basis of his life and what is important in it. Hence, he loses confidence in himself.

Education is a growing discipline. New dimensions that are emerge from Sathya Sai Baba's Philosophy will enriched and strengthened the present society in Philosophical, Sociological, Educational, Cultural and Developmental aspects. Philosophy of Sathya Sai Baba is a ray of hope for the future generation A few drops of the ocean of Sathya Sai Baba's teachings, an attempt to encapsulate its essence follows. Sathya Sai Baba urges mankind to: Believe in God - for there is only one God for all mankind, though He may be called by many names. Follow sincerely their respective religions and live their daily lives in consonance with the teachings of good behavior and morality. Educational Philosophy of Sri Satya Sai Baba contains all the essential features of Indian Culture and helped the mankind in many a crisis such as we are facing now-a-days.

Keywords: Bhagaban, Avatar, Incarnation, Sarvam, Kalpavriksha, Cosmic, Educare, EHV, SSEHV.

Our popular South Indian Guru, Spiritual Figure and Educator, Bhagawan Sri Sathya Sai Baba (1926-2011) has often emphasized that the purpose of education is to inculcate virtues and character in every individual. The philosophical cornerstone of Sathya Sai Education is the concept of **Educare**. Sri Sathya Sai Baba draws a distinction between what has traditionally been conceived to be 'education' and what he refers to as '**Educare**'. He says that educationists who merely read books and pass on the contents to students are not fulfilling the goals of real education. Rather, "real education is that which promotes unity, equality and peaceful co-existence with fellow human beings." It flows from the heart, and is termed as '**Educare**.' Therefore, "**Educare** should be pursued along with what has usually been meant by education." Education is a matter of questioning. Why this? Why not that? Why? How? What? But, Educare is not a question. It is a quest. Quest is different from question. Quest is a search. Quest is an enquiry. Quest involves turning inward. Quest requires one to go beyond the senses. Quest aims

to take you to your reality; Bhagavan wants **Educare** today. Now we have Educare to care for ourselves, and Educare to care for society. We have Educare to know our real identity, true nature and knowledge of the Self. Educare is care of the Self; the Supreme Self is **Educare**. The guiding principles of the term **Educare**, as used by Sri Sathya Sai Baba, are:- (a) divinity is love, and it is the undercurrent of all human values; (b) *Educare* elicits the inherent human values and translates them into action in daily life; (c) the purpose of education is for living a fully human and spiritual life; (d) the end of education is character and character manifests itself as the unity of thought, word, and deed.

Institutes of Sathya Sai Education were established to manage and oversee standards in the Sathya Sai Schools, to train teachers in Education in Human Values (**EHV**) and to form professional links (or partnerships) with government or private schools for EHV. They have the task of developing **EHV** programmes appropriate to their local culture, to create awareness and guide government schools to establish such programmes. Sathya Sai Education in Human Values was not complete in itself and in its place **EDUCARE** has become a comprehensive education for life; not only education, but also religion, spirituality and humanity. Human values make life worthwhile, noble, and excellent. Those qualities lie within the human personality, waiting to be drawn out and translated into action. Sathya Sai Education is based on five human values: **Truth, Right Conduct, Peace, Love, and Nonviolence**. Drawing out these five inherent human values develops good character. Sri Sathya Sai Baba regards the development of good character as the ultimate aim or end of education. Sathya Sai Education utilises as pedagogy of integral education that elicits human values through all aspects of education, including: the process of learning and the process of teaching, while integrating them into the curriculum, and the educational environment.

Educational philosophy of Bhagavan Sri Sathya Sai Baba is worth a revisit. In a rapidly changing world, where people are searching for roots and a sense of belonging, an important task of education is to help people to gain a stable identity. This can happen only when people can relate to values that are independent of time and space. The renewed emphasis on values in recent years could be viewed in this light. By eliciting the universal and timeless human values of love, peace, truth, right conduct and nonviolence, which bring together the profound moral insights of the world's great enduring civilizations. Sathya Sai Education helps to create a universal and unchanging frame of reference to give one a stable sense of identity. Sathya Sai Schools, colleges, universities and other medical and social organizations are based on these central features of Bhagavan's philosophy. They aim at human excellence through developing all personality domains – physical, intellectual, emotional, social and spiritual, and not just the intellectual. They are models of how human values can be integrated with the school curriculum to achieve the real aims of education – character development and academic excellence. Sathya Sai Baba says that "**The End of Education is Character**". Today the moral, ethical and spiritual values are on the decline. The modern students have no trace of these values in them. Sai Baba's emphasis is said to be on the development of the moral and human values in students, which are lacking in the present system. The worth of the educational reforms can be seen only in the way in which such reforms can transform the students admitted in random from different stratus of society, and how education is able to transform them.

Sathya Sai Baba has offered a veritable ocean of knowledge and guidance on all aspects of spiritual, religious, and value-oriented living and it is enough to put into practice in our day to day life. The real and worthy education is the society regards the culture, civilization and humanity as the central of all development. If philosophy is a reflection upon social ideals, education is an effort to actualize these ideals in human behaviour. In order to reach the

heights of its past glory in material and spiritual fields, a radical change in Indian Society is the need of the day. Perhaps it is not an exaggeration that teachers, parents, students, educationalists and political leaders—all these who are directly or indirectly concerned with education – are dissatisfied with the present system of education in India. Though some efforts have been made for the quantitative improvement of education, it has had its corresponding deterioration in the quality of education. We lost our values and failed to establish new values suitable to the modern times without detrimental to our culture. This research study will highlight how the ethos of a school can be improved thus leading to a learning and caring environment that will foster character building thus contributing towards academic excellence through the incorporation of basic universal values which are fundamental to The Sathya Sai Educational Philosophy and Education in Human Values (SSEHV) Programme. I further suggest that the history of his geographic locale, in which there are strong themes of sacred kingship and ecstatic, advaitic, poetic, devotional, sainthood, social, educational, may contributed to the production and reception of his persona.

In the world there is nothing as sacred as Janna, the highest knowledge. There is nothing more precious in the world than true education. It reveals the divinity that sustains the universe and promotes the welfare of mankind materially, mentally and socially. Only through education do we understand creation and the truth about humanity. Those who realize the nature of the Divine can know the relationship between Nature, Society and the infinite potential of man. Instead of being subject to Nature, man can acquire through education the knowledge to utilize the forces of Nature. Thereby the highest bliss can be experienced. IN the educational system today, the spiritual element has no place. This can not be true education. Education must proceed primarily from the spirit to Nature. It must show that mankind constitutes one Divine family. The divinity that is present in society can be experienced only through individuals. Education today, however, ends with the acquisition of degrees. Real education should enable one to utilize the knowledge one has acquired to meet the challenges of life and to make all human beings happy as far as possible. Born in society, one has the duty to work for the welfare and progress of society.

The present system of Education is fast sliding into the depths of degradation. Freedom has led to licentiousness; reverence has receded from all relationships; institutions dedicated to the worship of the Goddess of Learning have changed into temples for the worship of the Goddess of Wealth. Teachers who teach with the salary paid to them in their minds, students who learn with the jobs they may procure in their minds are both pursuing wrong paths. Appreciation and encouragement are offered not for virtue and good character, but for money and its accumulation. In the conduct of individuals and in human relationships, no trace of morality, charity, justice or rectitude are visible. The situation is fraught with enormous danger for the future of humanity. Life today is riddled with fear, despair and doubt. Man rolls uneasily on a bed infested with fleas, finding no rest or peace.

The most distinguishing feature of Sathya Sai educational system is its philosophy that helping students develop a good character is equal in importance to fostering the development of skills that will help them to earn a good living. Revolutionary in concept and comprehensive in scope, Sathya Sai educational principles have become a lifelong learning and transformation process for children, men, and women in all parts of the world. His message to the students is: “ **The end of Education is character and Education without character is useless.**” Sathya Sai Baba is a highly revered spiritual leader and world teacher, whose life and message are inspiring millions of people throughout the world to turn God-ward and to lead more purposeful and moral lives. His timeless and universal teachings, along with the manner in which he leads

his own life, are attracting seekers of Truth from all the religions of the world. Yet, he is not seeking to start a new religion. Nor does he wish to direct followers to any particular religion. Sathya Sai Baba places great importance on proper education for young people. Parents and community leaders are urged to concern themselves with the informal as well as the formal experiences to which their children and young adults are exposed. He has established a model education system, which includes primary schools, secondary schools, and an accredited university with three campuses, offering undergraduate, Masters, and Ph.D. degrees. No fees are charged to students, and admission is open to all, regardless of race, religion, or economic condition. In addition to emphasizing the pursuit of academic excellence, Sathya Sai Baba's system of "integral education" is designed to foster self-discipline and pro-social conduct.

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